

Rare Currents: A Thematic Survey of Historical Marine Life Clippings from the Monterey Peninsula Herald (1938-1986)

Compiled & written by:

Hannah Phetbourom, undergraduate researcher (haphetbou@gmail.com)

under the guidance of

Michael Montgomery, PhD candidate, UCSB Marine Science and Environmental Studies

Affiliation:

University of California, Santa Barbara

Ecology, Evolution, and Marine Biology; Environmental Studies Program; Department of

Anthropology

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I. INTRODUCTION

“There is nothing abnormal about turtle tears.”

This project was undertaken as part of an ongoing investigation into cultural and ecological perceptions of environmental change, particularly in relation to warm water events like El Niño. Monterey Bay is a place where those changes are both biologically visible and strongly socially narrated, as unusual visitors wash ashore, fishing conditions shift, and people talk about what the ocean is “doing” any given year. The analysis that is presented here is based on marine-related articles published in the *Monterey Peninsula Herald* that report sightings of rare or “tropical” marine species, unusual animal behaviors, and community reactions to changing conditions along the Central Californian coast.

What emerged from this collection were not only patterns of warm water-linked anomalies, but also a rich and tender record of the ways humans observe and interpret the living ocean. Newspapers take stories and turn them into tales that are intended to resonate with humans, with the characters in this instance being none other than the marine life itself. In one

widely covered case, wharf aquarium¹ owner Nelson “Bill” Hyler had reassured concerned visitors that there is “nothing abnormal about turtle tears” when a leatherback turtle, nicknamed Alfred, appeared to be crying in its tank.² In another, a local whale-watcher suggested that a group of killer whales lingering along the shore was simply “just snooping.”³ Each article, in its own way, reflects a layered interaction between environmental conditions, memory, and community identity.

The following sections are a summarized but sincere attempt to honor and preserve that narrative record. While not intended as a formal academic paper, it serves as an organizational overview of the clippings, offering insight into what was found and why it might be valuable—not only to researchers, but to the coastal communities who have long lived beside and on these waters.

II. METHODOLOGY

This paper is drawing on a small, curated archive of mid-20th-century newspaper coverage from the *Monterey Peninsula Herald (MPH)*, spanning roughly the late 1930s through the 1980s.⁴ The articles were originally retrieved by Michael Montgomery, a PhD researcher in environmental science, in collaboration with the archivists and reference librarians at the Monterey Public Library, as part of a broader project on how coastal communities perceive and remember warm-water events. In total, the collection of articles comprises just over fifty marine-

¹ The aquarium that is referred to in these articles, and throughout this text, is the earlier wharf aquarium on Fishermen’s Wharf, not the Monterey Bay Aquarium, which opened in 1984.

² Fred Sorri, “One-ton Turtle Captured in Bay,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, August 30, 1961, Sheet #70.

³ “9 Killer ‘Whales Off Coast,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, April 15, 1963, Sheet #87; “Killers are Real, Ferocious Whales,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, April 17, 1963, Sheet #87.

⁴ All newspaper clippings underlying this study can be accessed by appointment at the California History Room, Monterey Public Library, Monterey, CA.

[https://monterey.gov/library/library_services/research/history_room/index.php]

related clippings, focused on local news items that described unusual marine species sightings, alongside reports that explicitly linked coastal observations to warm water or other anomalous ocean conditions. For this study, I worked from photocopies of these articles, recording recurring descriptive phrases, the tone of coverage, and the roles that are played by different speakers.

The analysis that follows is qualitative and interpretive rather than statistical. Articles were grouped into broad thematic categories: warm-water visitors and unusual presence, references to past events, emotional and moral framings of marine animals, and the interplay between scientific authority and public spectacle. These themes structure the “Key Findings” sections below. Because the archive is limited to a single local newspaper, and to articles that editors have judged newsworthy in the past, the material is not a comprehensive record of all unusual events in Monterey Bay. Instead, it is a focused window into how certain phenomena were selected, described, and made meaningful in public discourse at the time.

III. KEY FINDINGS

a. Warm Water and Tropical Visitors

From the 1930s onwards, *MPH* coverage repeatedly returned to reports of marine visitors that seemed startlingly out of place, both to regular civilians and to those who are familiar with the marine ecosystem of Monterey. Basking sharks in the harbor, great white sharks at the wharf, giant squid on city beaches, and sunfish too large to sell were all treated as unusual visitors, even when scientists noted that some of these species were not entirely unknown to the region. At the same time, truly rare or more southerly species like tropical crabs, warm-water fishes, or leatherback turtles, appeared in ways that local observers and scientists increasingly linked to changes in ocean temperature and currents. These visitors were described frequently as “bizarre,”

“southern strangers,” or “rare warm-water creatures.” Rather than turning up in the expected context of scientific surveys, these organisms had been detected in casual, often surprised observations of fishermen, beachgoers, and local staff of the wharf aquarium. They saw that species normally associated with warmer climates were found in various states of having drifted ashore, being tangled in nets, or simply just gliding through the temperate waters just off the Monterey coast.

Some of the earliest articles in the archive highlight organisms that are ordinarily associated either with deeper water, or a more southerly range. In 1943, for example, Dr. Rolf Bolin, a researcher at Hopkins Marine Station, had reported on a “rare crab that swims” (*Euphylax dovii*) in Monterey harbor, noting that it had previously been thought to range only from Central America to Chile.⁵ Another 1946 piece described large numbers of *Carinaria*, transparent, snail-like planktonic animals, appearing near Fishermen’s Wharf alongside salps, with Bolin attributing their presence close to shore to an influx of deep-sea waters.⁶ In the same period, giant squid normally known from Alaska waters (*Moroteuthis robusta*) and rarely seen in California were found on Monterey’s beaches, in two instances about a decade apart (1932 and 1946).⁷ These mid-century reports already frame unusual visitors as the product of shifting water masses, even where temperature is not explicitly mentioned.

By the late 1950s, *MPH* coverage came to make warming itself a central part of the story in some articles. In a 1959 article titled “*Peninsula Some Day a Tropical Area*,” fisheries investigator Peter Glynn describes a set of “rare” or warm-water fishes, including ocean

⁵ Rolf Bolin, “Rare Crab That Swims Found Here: Strange Sea Creature Added to Collection of Local Marine Station,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, December 16, 1943, Sheet #19.

⁶ “‘Jellyfish’ was Really a Sea Snail: Rare Creatures in Bay for One day: Described by Bolin,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, April 2, 1946, Sheet #25.

⁷ “Giant Squid Found on City Beach,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, July 17, 1946, Sheet #25.

whitefish, kelp bass, halfmoon, opaleye, and sheephead, all turning up in Peninsula waters where he had “never” seen some of them before.⁸ He points to long-term measurements showing the average water temperature rising from 51.8°F to 55.4°F over five years, and links this change to shifts in plankton, sardines, whales, and shark encounters. Glynn and his colleagues had offered two possible explanations at the time: a general warming of the earth due to greater discharge of carbon dioxide, and a shift in ocean currents that might be diverting part of the warm Japanese current closer to the Northern Californian coast. In other words, by 1959, local scientific voices were already connecting Monterey’s “tropical” visitors to both global climate processes and regional circulation.

The early 1960s then brought several highly visible events that further solidified the relationship between unusual species and warmer waters. In January 1960, the Herald reported that thousands of galatheid crabs, which are deep-sea relatives of squat lobsters, had made what biologists described as only their second ever recorded “trip” to the Peninsula, the first having been in 1859.⁹ Biologists at Hopkins Marine Station could not definitively explain the appearance, but one state biologist suggested that the crabs have been “pinched off in a finger of warmer water” and then wafted ashore by currents, while another source pointed to recent Northern California storms as a possible influence. In 1961, an article on “swarming brown jellyfish” described *Chrysaora medusae* arriving in such abundance that the bottom of the water could not be seen, making note that their numbers had not been matched since 1957, and emphasized their movement being affected by currents and tides.¹⁰ Here, these pieces show

⁸ Mac Bowe, “Peninsula Some Day a Tropical Area: Long-range Forecast from Briny Deep,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, December 13, 1159, Sheet #52.

⁹ Dave Epperson, “Thousands of Tiny Crabs Make Rare Visit to Peninsula,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, January 13, 1960, Sheet #5.

¹⁰ “Swarming Brown Jellyfish Periodic Mystery in Monterey Bay,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, January 18, 1961, Sheet #61.

scientists and reporters treating warm or displaced water masses as key drivers of visible anomalies along the shore.

Figure 1: *Grimothea planipes*, believed in mid-1900s to be once-a-century visitors¹¹

Pelagic red crabs (*Grimothea planipes*) (Figure 1), the galatheid crabs referenced earlier, provide one of the clearest long-term examples of how the Herald framed warm-water visitors. One article dated in 1973 referred to them as “once-in-a-century” guests, recording that they had last been seen in Monterey Bay from 1957 to 1960, and prior to that, in 1859, as previously noted.¹¹ This same piece explains that scientists are “convinced” the crabs appear whenever the water is warm enough, and cites biologist Tom Hardwick, who attributes the 1972-1973 influx to unusually warm bay temperatures, an active Davidson Current bringing warm water northward, and southerly winds helping to maintain those conditions. In this case, an invertebrate species that is usually associated with Mexico and Baja California becomes a visible indicator of warmer-than-usual water along the central California coast. Alongside these occurrences, sea turtles, especially leatherbacks, take on a similar role in the 1960s and the 1970s. In August 1961, ex-mayor Dan Searle and three companions caught a 1,200-pound leatherback sea turtle

¹¹ “Peninsula Sea Temperature Key to Seldom-Seen Crab,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, January 22, 1973, Sheet #120.

off Monterey. Bolin, who continuously appears throughout the articles, described Pacific leatherbacks as “warm water beasts” and suggested that warm currents flowing north from Mexico since the late 1950s could explain its presence.¹² Later that same month, sports fishing skipper Jerry Lemon captured another leatherback (the one who later came to be nicknamed Alfred, and kept in the wharf aquarium), alive in Monterey Bay, roughly 500 miles north of the species’ usual habitat. Bolin once again connected the sighting to a pathway of warm current that had been present since 1958. Then, in 1973, an article on an 800-pound sea turtle carcass, reported as the first such “giant sea turtle” found in Monterey in about fifteen years, shows that large turtles continued to be treated as rare, but recurring visitors.¹³ By 1986, Alan Baldrige, librarian of the Hopkins Marine Station at the time, made notes that tropical leatherback turtles were turning up in “greater numbers than usual” along the Monterey County coast, with five sightings by early July compared to the one or two typically recorded in a year.¹⁴ Baldrige emphasized that this did not mean leatherbacks were abundant, but instead tied their presence to a seasonal movement from tropical breeding grounds into Monterey Bay.

The 1980s also brought in more explicit discussion of warm-water marine animals and early references to El Niño (even if not by that name every time). A 1986 piece titled “*Tropical Sea Mammals Sighted*” contains descriptions of courting gray whales observed alongside abnormally large numbers of common dolphins and frigate birds, both of which are typically associated with more tropical waters.¹⁵ Baldrige is quoted as saying that “it’s really strange that they should be up here,” remarking that it is too early to tell whether their presence so far north

¹² “Bay Yields Giant Sea Turtle,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, August 14, 1961, Sheet #6.

¹³ “Giant Sea Turtle Found in Monterey,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, September 3, 1973, Sheet #12.

¹⁴ “Tropical Leatherback Turtle Sightings Increase Along Coast,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, July 12, 1986, Sheet #254.

¹⁵ “Tropical Sea Mammals Sighted: Dolphins Off Monterey Coast,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, March 15, 1986, Sheet #244.

indicates that another El Niño is developing. Around the same period, other articles report distressed common dolphins coming ashore in waters described as “too cold to be inviting,” further emphasizing how particular species are used to gauge whether Monterey Bay is behaving more like a tropical-water or temperate-water system in a specific season.

Across these decades, the explanatory language in *MPH* shifts from relatively simple mentions of “storms” and “influxes of deep-sea water” to more explicit attention to warming trends, altered currents, and named climate phenomena. While not always including references to scientific reasoning, many of these sightings were, either directly or indirectly, still attributed to warmer ocean temperatures flowing through the Monterey waters. Writers and quoted scientists alike treat red crabs, jellyfish swarms, and leatherback turtles as visible proxies for change in the physical environment around Monterey Bay. At the very same time, these animals also get presented as singular events—“once-in-a-century visitors,” “the largest ever caught,” creatures being seen “for the first time in thirty years,” effectively turning them into memorable markers of particular warm-water years. How these events are remembered and thus woven into a sense of local ecological time becomes the focus of the next section.

b. Local Memory and Cyclical Time

Beyond marking physical change in Monterey Bay, unusual marine visitors also organize how local people speak about time. Within this *MPH* archive, marine anomalies are rarely presented as isolated surprises. Instead, they are repeatedly situated within a remembered sequence of past events, creating a sense of cyclical, rather than purely linear, time. The articles contain anchorings such as “once every century,” “not seen since [...],” or “first time in [...],” and these phrases are notably doing two things at once. They are both positioning a present-day

event within a longer scientific record, and also narrating it as the return of something socially remembered. The appearances of galathied red crabs are one of the clearest examples of this. In 1960, articles described “thousands of tiny crabs” making their second ever trip to the Peninsula, with them also being “thrown ashore in considerable numbers in 1859 at Monterey Bay.” Then, in 1973, during another influx of *Pleuroncodes planipes*, they are referenced with their status being once-every-century visitors, recalling their presence from 1957-1960, and before that, in 1859. With each new arrival, the crabs are explicitly tied to earlier episodes, so that a warm-water year in the 1970s is narrated through events more than a century old. This archive of newspaper folders, and the scientists and journalists writing in it, are actively stitching those dates together. Similar temporal anchoring appears across other species that have been previously mentioned. *Chrysaora* “swept into Monterey Bay in numbers not [seen] since 1957,” and the article that writes this frames the event as the latest instance in a periodic, recurring mystery, rather than an entirely new phenomenon. The 1946 story on *Carinaria* and other unusual plankton had included mention of a local wharf oil dealer, Archie Sanchez, who claimed that he had never seen such creatures in his 30 years of living in the area, whilst biological laboratory owner Ed Ricketts recalled that the last time such large quantities of plankton were observed in the bay was April 1924. Coverage of the leatherback turtles in the 1960s quoted “Old-timers” on Fishermen’s Wharf, who say that the last comparable specimen had been brought in decades earlier.¹⁶ Rather than these details being incidental or mundanely recorded, these articles are routinely and deliberately measuring surprise by counting backwards.

This layering of recollection comes from both professional and vernacular sources. Scientist such as Bolin repeatedly ground their identifications in the small number of prior

¹⁶ Mac Bowe, “Giant Turtle Caught Near Monterey: SALMON FISHERMAN LAND A BIG ONE,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, Sheet #69.

specimens they have seen. In a piece on the rare ragfish, *Acrotus willoughbyi*, Bolin notes that in “eleven years” in Monterey, he would certainly have heard of an oddity at this level if it had been found before, and that this is instead the first specimen of the species he has personally seen.¹⁷ Everyday witnesses, like wharf workers, fish market owners, or long-term residents, all offer their own time scales in a different sort of language, making the claim that there used to be many green turtles in the bay years ago but they died out recently, or saying that it’s the “first time in three years” seeing killer whales off a particular stretch of the coast. Altogether, these statements are forming a local chronicle of change that is not dependent on any formal monitoring programs, and yet still tracks intervals, returns, and absences with striking consistency.

By the decades of the 1970s and 1980s, this habit of looking backward converges with emerging climate language. When Hardwick explains the 1972-1973 pelagic crab influx, he does so partly by invoking past appearances, and partly by pointing to unusually warm bay temperatures, an active Davidson current, and winds coming from the south. The comments made by Baldridge similarly lean on both pattern and memory, raising the possibility that another El Niño may be developing, precisely because the constitution of animals resembles past warm-water years. In these later articles, local ecological time is distinctly cyclical and repetitive. Strange visitors arrive in clusters that then remind observers of earlier clusters, which are now being read against named phenomena like El Niño. Crucially, this ecological memory is not something that is limited to those with advanced biological training, or a technical understanding of marine science. These are not formal longitudinal datasets, or articles exclusively only doing interviews with those who would know exactly what species is appearing

¹⁷ Albert Campbell, “Rare Ragfish is Landed by Fisherman: Salinas Man Affords Scientists Look at *Acrotus Willoughbyi*,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, May 21, 1940, Sheet #17.

and why they might be there. These are informal, and very local observations, being preserved through anecdotal sharing and socialization that occurred at the time. These warm-water visitors, whenever they turned up, were not just anomalies to many, but instead were meaningful stories that got passed down through conversation and physical recordings such as singular clippings taken from larger newspapers, accumulating a locally held archive of oceanic change. It also becomes apparent throughout the articles that there is an underlying feeling of uncertainty—many times, civilians or researchers talk as if they feel the sea was doing something or acting in a way it was not supposed to. These warm-water visitors arrived without warning, some of them already dead when found. In the earliest reports of the Herald, the presence of these organisms was very significant even if no one could clearly note why. Marine anomalies are measured against this collective memory as they are similarly measured against scientific baselines. Collected newspapers depict fishermen, beachgoers, skindivers, and shopkeepers all contributing time-stamped markers, such as how long they have lived in the area, how often they have seen a particular species, and when exactly the last one of its kind appeared. These observations may not always supply precise dates, but they help define what counts as normal or exceptional in local waters. Scientific voices then extend that temporal frame further, reaching back to 19th-century records or linking present-day sightings to long-term physical trends. The result is a very layered sense of time, in which these events of jellyfish swarms, or crab abundance, and other species act as recurring characters in a regional story of change. Each new appearance is a fresh event, but also a reminder—of 1859, of “that one year in the late 1950s,” of previous El Niño seasons, and of what longtime residents say they used to see.

In this way, local memory and ecological observation are tightly intertwined all throughout history. People on the Central California coast are not stopping at observations that

the ocean looks different, or is acting different. These observations always come alongside memories of when things last looked this way, and recording so in print. Those patterns of speech (“once every century,” “not seen since [...],” “first time in [...])” turn marine anomalies into markers of time, and preserve cycles of marine change in headlines and casual quotations long before these cycles have the chance to be plotted in any formal dataset. They are consistent, often featuring the same recurring speakers or making references to an exact past article, and reflect an ongoing awareness of change and rhythm in the ocean, even if the underlying biological processes behind all these cycles remain unknown to the majority. Years of education or a degree are not required to pass on what one has noticed to the next generation, or to explain what it means to you personally and not a scientific journal. This kind of remembering travels through conversations and shared meals, and through to refrigerator doors or passed from hand to hand.

c. Emotional Tone, Public Fascination

Species in these articles are not met with neutrality. What is especially striking in the tone of these articles is the common mixture of awe and apprehension. They are received almost like characters in an ongoing drama, as they are recognizable, interpreted, and reacted to accordingly, depending on the roles that people feel they play. Their appearances are interpreted through emotional and moral lenses rather than described as purely biological facts. Some of these arrivals are welcomed, some are treated as alarming, and others are framed as the tragic victims of a larger story. Coverage of shark-killed otters off Carmel in 1958 emphasizes “man-eating sharks” and the tally of dead animals along the coast, casting otters as vulnerable innocents, and

sharks as dangerous antagonists.¹⁸ A piece from 1972, focused on another instance of sea otter pups being killed, this time during a severe winter storm, similarly foregrounds the fragility of young sea otters at Whaler's Cove, and debates whether human disturbance may have contributed to their deaths.¹⁹ In these types of stories, the tone of the coverage leans toward sorrow and concern, asking (or more so, directly prompting) readers to care about individual animals and to worry about what has gone wrong. By contrast, when thousands of pelagic red crabs swarm the shoreline to the degree of being like a carpet on the beach, or when a 1,200-pound sunfish is hauled in by a local baker and then cast adrift due to the lack of a market for it, the language then starts to swing toward awe, absurdity, or even dismissiveness. The very same ocean that produces grief in one article can produce laughter or shocked delight in another. This emotional language reflects the way human meaning is assigned to nonhuman lives, analyzing them by parameters we live by. Instead of animals being mere organisms in these clippings, they become visitors, victims, predators, nuisances, miracles, and more, all based entirely on how people see them.

The range of these reactions is rarely portrayed as distant. Many of the most vivid articles describe people gathering at the shoreline out of what is a mix of scientific curiosity, and also heavy fascination and the desire to simply see something extraordinary. The pelagic red crab appearance of 1960 is described as drawing high numbers of people, with residents crowding the beach to observe, or even catch the crabs themselves. Reports of great white sharks, killer whales, and giant turtles regularly mention fishermen, wharf workers, tourists, and children all gathering around the catch or sighting. A story on a "*Man-Eater*" shark published in 1938

¹⁸ "Sharks Killing Otters off Carmel, Says Savant" *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, March 6, 1958, Sheet #4.

¹⁹ Jim Larimore, "Severe Storm May Have Killed Otter Pups, State Biologist Says," *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, December 19, 1972, Sheet #119.

remarks that the fish had caused a “big stir” among workers on Fishermen’s Wharf and local swimmers, even as experts reassured the public that sharks such as the one caught “rarely” range that far north.²⁰ When the leatherback turtle that was nicknamed Alfred is brought alive into a tank on Fishermen’s Wharf, spectators immediately respond to his size, his movement, and also his apparent “tears.” Families with children, fishermen coming off of their boats, and tourists that are walking the wharf at that time, all find themselves pulled toward the same spot in the sand or on the pier, at the very same time. These gatherings are almost ritualistic; people hear that something strange has arrived, and they go to see it. Crowds of individuals stand together, looking down at perhaps a sunfish, or a giant turtle, or any kind of creature in an unfortunate state, and even those who know little about marine biology recognize the underlying understanding that something is “wrong,” or something “unusual” is happening at the moment.

Figure 2: a young boy enjoys his ride on the back of a giant (deceased) sea turtle²¹

²⁰ “‘Man-Eater’ Shark Creates Big Sensation at Old Wharf Today,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, December 31, 1938, Sheet #11.

²¹ “Bay Yields Giant Sea Turtle,” *MPH*, Aug. 14, 1961, Sheet #6.

The responses that are described in the article are often immediate, and also physical. Although the clippings do not always spell out crowd reactions in detail, they repeatedly hint at gasps, anxious questions, and disgusted reactions in certain scenarios. Children, meanwhile, are seen posing for photographs next to large animals (Figure 2) while the adults discuss (or argue) about what exactly the creature is or what its presence could “mean.” In coverage on Alfred, as previously referenced, spectators expressing concern that the turtle was “crying” prompted aquarium owner Bill Hyler to reassure them that there is “nothing abnormal about turtle tears.” This initial, bodily reaction that represents either wonder, fear, or disgust, works to translate animal behavior into a language of personality, and this happens well before any technical explanation can begin to catch up. Observers, first and foremost, reach for human narratives that make emotional sense. Ecological disruption is experienced as a public spectacle rather than as a quiet shift in population numbers, or a quiet shift in ocean temperature. A mysterious fish becomes “that monster brought into the harbor” that one day, and these are the memories that persist most strongly.

Figure 3: aquarium owner Nelson “Bill” Hyler and Alfred²²

²² Sorri, “One-ton Turtle Captured in Bay,” *MPH*, Aug. 30, 1961, Sheet #70.

The language used to describe these animals pushes this framing further, with creatures rarely ever being described in neutral terms. Sea turtles are calm visitors, or gentle giants, whose presence alone is a privilege, whales are “snoopy” and curious, otters are rediscovered survivors and later beloved coastal residents, and sharks are titled “man-eaters” that take upon the role of killers of charismatic mammals. Even physiological details that are entirely normal, such as salt excreted from a turtle’s eyes, are reframed as recognizable signs of sadness. The articles referencing killer whales seen near Lovers Point emphasizes their “unpredictable” feeding habits and poor eyesight while advising people to stay out of the water for the time being, showing that danger is described in narrative terms as much as ecological ones.

Figure 4: onlookers rush to keep a stranded dolphin wet and shaded from sun²³

With this being said, it is undeniable that not all species are received equally, and emotional response is shaped by perceived value that comes in the form of beauty, intelligence,

²³ “Distressed Common Dolphin Found on Del Monte Beach,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, April 27, 1981, Sheet #145A.

or usefulness. Sea turtles, whales, and sea otters, all species that are either large or visually striking and all easily anthropomorphized, often elicit tones of sorrow or admiration. The 1973 coverage that focused on the discovery of a dead giant sea turtle makes note of its size and rarity, and includes debate on what should be done with the carcass, suggesting a sense that something important has been lost. Otters, a species once thought extinct and later rediscovered along the Monterey County coast, effectively move from being targets of exploitation to symbols of coastal recovery. Their deaths, when discovered, are heavily mourned, and any strandings that happen read as heart-wrenching tragedies. And when a dolphin is found alive but distressed on a local beach, it is met with immediate rescue efforts and veterinary care rather than any indifference.²⁴ (Figure 4) These species are ones that slide easily into the role of “worthy” victims. By contrast, smaller or less “charming” organisms often receive a different kind of treatment. A giant sunfish that was caught in 1938 is described as “grotesque,” (Figure 5) and thus having no market, causing it to be thrown back out.²⁵ Therefore, the ocean anomaly of a significantly larger creature of a species being found, which would almost certainly prompt a mass crowd gathering if it were, say, a turtle, then amounts to nothing other than waste when it is another kind of animal. When swarms of jellyfish are reported, they are complained about, said to make the bay’s surface “brown,” entirely obscuring the bottom and fouling fishermen’s nets. Species like these are mostly curiosities, nuisances at worst, instead of being individuals that provoke grief and are thought about in-depth, loved for generations. The pelagic red crabs, despite being rare visitors with an almost mythical sort of status in the community, are handled and scooped into buckets to be eaten or used as bait, and they are as much a resource or oddity as much as they are indicators of ocean change. Even marine mammals are not uniformly

²⁴ “Distressed Common Dolphin Found on Del Monte Beach,” *MPH*, Apr. 27, 1981, Sheet #145A.

²⁵ “Sunfish Also Rises From Monterey Bay” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, August 24, 1938, Sheet #11.

protected—in the 1940s, sea lions were heavily framed in a couple of articles as net-destroying pests, presenting the state’s authorization to take them for oil and meal as a justified response to the longstanding complaints of fishermen.²⁶ Another notable article includes a Pacific Grove gardener who expressed the belief that a small group of skindivers were wrecking the underwater display of marine life, “cleaning out” the abalone and urchins that once drew thousands of visitors each year.²⁷ Here, in this instance, invertebrates, which are organisms that historically do not see much anthropomorphizing, are valued because they contribute to a scenic display. The emotional weight that is attached to a species depends on how it fits into human desires and expectations. People may name a large turtle when it washes up dead, and visit it repeatedly, following news about what will be done with the body (resulting in its mention in multiple articles over the years), but in contrast, smaller or less charismatic species often get treated as background occurrences.

Figure 5: large sunfish is pulled onto the wharf, later dubbed “grotesque” and thrown back²⁸

²⁶ “Sea Lions Cause Trouble for Some Fisherman,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, May 23, 1981, Sheet #148; “Aerial Survey Preliminary to Campaign Against Sea Lions,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, March 12, 1948, Sheet #23; “Sea Lions to be Taken for Reduction: Commission Finds Offshore Herds Have Doubled in Year,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, June 27, 1946, Sheet #25.

²⁷ “Skindivers Blamed for Loss of Marine Life” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, September 5, 1961, Sheet #70.

²⁸ “Sunfish Also Rises From Monterey Bay,” *MPH*, Aug. 24, 1938, Sheet #11.

These differences in emotional response anticipate later patterns of environmentalism and conservation in modern society. Even before the idea of large megafauna being more charismatic to the public eye was a known issue in conservation biology, the public imagination was already naturally inclined to ranking animals according to, purely, how easy it is to care about them. Turtles and sea otters, with their perceived innocence and expressiveness, become obvious candidates for sympathy, organized campaigns, and persistent memory. Sharks, killer whales, and predatory marine mammals are cast as villains, or at the very least, as morally ambiguous figures that one should still be cautious around, if not entirely avoid. Jellyfish, pelagic crabs, plankton, and extraordinary fish like the ragfish and sunfish rarely come to occupy the same moral spotlight, even when their appearances are just as ecologically unusual. It is easy to dismiss what is being said in these articles as simply inaccurate from a biological perspective. Of course, animals are not literally crying from emotion, or “snooping” in the way we understand it as human behavior. But in these articles, the anthropomorphic language that is used goes a step beyond misdescribing factual biology, and moves into organizing moral attention. To write and publish that a turtle is “crying” is to invite compassion. To call a shark a “man-eater” is to invite fear, and possibly retribution.

Taken together, these emotional framings shape which events the community remembers most strongly, which species it feels personally responsible for, and which changes in the ocean feel like personal, lived loss versus background shifts that can fade without comment or consequence. The *MPH* articles from the past depict that public fascination with marine events is much more than simple curiosity about unusual animals, expanding into an ongoing process of assigning the roles of victim or villain, nuisance or spectacle, and of then deciding whose presence in the ocean matters enough to become stories that endure.

d. Science vs. Spectacle

Throughout these stories of rare visitors and strange events can be found a quieter narrative about expertise, relating to who is asked to explain the ocean, and how those explanations come to sit right alongside public fascination. Certain names recur through the newspaper clippings, as referenced throughout the paper: there are biologists such as Dr. Rolf Bolin and Tom Hardwick, state Fish and Game officials like Peter Glynn, and other strong figures of the Monterey community, like Alan Baldrige. Over time, these individuals become familiar figures within the text. They are the people who can enter a setting and translate what is a “mystery fish” or “monster squid” into something with a Latin name, with a known geographical range, and with an explanation for being present. Their very presence gives the articles an air of authority; a fisherman might bring in a ribbonfish that no one else on the wharf recognizes, but once Bolin is consulted, it becomes an unusually large “King of the Salmon,”²⁹ or a rare ragfish, such as the earlier referenced *Acrotus willoughbyi* that was also identified by Bolin, with only a handful of other previous records along the coast. What begins as a spectacle can be converted into evidence, positioning the specimen within a larger, scientific pattern.

At the same time, however, these scientific voices are never truly the only ones in the room. The newspaper articles are also full of people like fishermen, aquarium owners, harbor workers, and even casual beachgoers offering their own assessments. In a situation where fishermen, who have spent decades on the water, could possibly be inclined to think that an abundance of sea lions is directly taking money or food from their catches, a biologist may instead respond more cautiously, warning that any large-scale killing of sea lions would threaten

²⁹ “Rare Fish Found by Local Man: ‘King of Salmon’ is Third Caught Here Since April,” *Monterey Peninsula Herald*, November 7, 1946, Sheet #25.

local populations, or remind readers that many of these predators have always been present, only now they are being noticed differently. This tension between local certainty, and scientific uncertainty, is subtle, but consistent all throughout decades of writing. The community often frames its interpretations as obvious and self-evident, but scientists, in contrast, are much more likely to use phrasing like “may be linked to,” “perhaps due to,” or “could have been.” This contrast becomes especially visible in episodes that blur most strongly into spectacle. The articles repeatedly note how a single animal can become the center of a public scene, with scientists both participating in and moderating the social drama. When a crab “forgets to crawl on the bottom like a normal crab and begins to swim like a fish,” Bolin announces that this is a confirmation that “news has happened,” deliberately adopting the newspaper’s theatrical voice even as he carefully identifies the animal as *Euphylax dovii*, providing deeper insight into its normal geographical range. In the case of the turtle Alfred being kept alive in an aquarium tank, both Hyler and Bolin are quoted weighing in on the animal’s age, species, and the warm current that has created a pathway north since 1958. Yet, the article also dwells on the turtle’s size, his unusual presence “500 miles north” of his usual habitat, and the crowds gathering to watch the turtle and press up close to the glass, drawn in partly by the impression that Alfred is “crying.” In that article, our introducing quote, “*There is nothing abnormal about turtle tears,*” is corrective, moving in as a scientific explanation meant to deflate sentimental misunderstanding, explaining the salt secretion around the eyes as routine osmoregulation, challenging the idea that the animal seems to be crying from emotion in a way that is notably similar and recognizable to us. Still, this correction, whilst standing as an offered scientific perspective, does not disperse the emotional setting of the scene overall, and scientific explanation in this instance is folded into the

performance instead of standing as a replacement for it, and the turtle remains a spectacle to be watched and commented on, even as his physiology is clarified.

Shark and killer whale coverage makes this tension even sharper at times. Shark encounters, for example, are some of the most charged examples, written with language such as “man-eater,” “killer shark,” and “great danger to swimmers.” Headlines lean heavily into emotional fear, turning a single shark encounter or sighting into a looming threat. Within these interactions, however, biologists tend to take the natural approach of downplaying this framing, again making note of the fact that these great white or other large shark species have patrolled these waters for a very long time now, and attacks on humans in comparison to their consistent presence remain rare. Here, the scientist’s role becomes one of softening the moral story that is pre-attached to the animal by many, instead redirecting attention from intentional “evil,” to ecological behavior with clear, logical explanations. In the 1958 report on “*Sharks Killing Otters off Carmel*,” Robert Orr, a curator of the California Academy of Science, had framed great white sharks as potential major causes of recent otter deaths, linking their northward movement to warmer coastal waters, whilst still acknowledging that these inferences are probabilistic rather than definitive proof. In these cases, scientists complicate what is often a dramatic storyline, rather than outright canceling it. Despite these efforts, the dramatic language is what lingers most strongly, and readers may remember extreme phrases like “man-eater” more than they remember a scientist’s careful and nuanced caveats. Their emphasis on range or behavior offers an ecological explanation, but it is affective language such as “ferocious” and “killer” that headlines carry forward. This same pattern often appears in coverage of whales offshore. A pod seen near a headland may get described as “prowling,” or simply “snooping around,” depending on who exactly is speaking. The mind of a naturalist might suggest that the whales are only following

prey, or taking advantage of changing conditions within the water, but people who are casual observers, meanwhile, can instead speak as if these are animals that are deliberately invading “our” waters or behaving in concerning, unusual ways, even when their presence is well within their historical range. Whilst scientific commentary is constantly folded into the story, it is never necessarily the sole definer of the situation, and the organisms of these articles are, all at once, research subjects, tourist attractions, and “characters” in a sort of developing marine folklore.

When it comes to warm-water anomalies and rare species appearances around the bay, the negotiation between science and spectacle starts to become even more striking. In certain clippings, scientists pass over surprisingly prescient ideas for their era: if the ocean continues to warm, waters off central California might someday resemble those farther south, leading to shifts in currents that could be redirecting branches of warm water into Monterey Bay, altering the basic conditions of the surrounding sea as they know it. These statements—along with previous mentions of scientists attributing certain ecological phenomena to named climate mechanisms such as the strength of the Davidson Current—are incredibly significant hypotheses, especially given the decades in which they were raised, and yet they are introduced gently in these reports, almost as side notes within articles that are otherwise about a single turtle, a single crab event, or a single odd fish. The readers’ attention is always, first and foremost, anchored to the image of an animal on a beach or within a tank, and the broader casual language regarding ecological phenomena falls into the pattern of receding and becoming part of the background narrative rather than worthy of a headline.

In this way, science, as how it is featured in these articles, often appears as something that both relies on, and at times, defers to spectacle. Biological explanations are always present, often with nuance and impressively forward-looking for their era, but they are also always

carried inside stories that are, on a fundamental level, much more about feeling something in response to a creature that should not be here, or not in this abundance, or not in this state of being. When a dead whale washes ashore, or a large turtle is tanked, or a swarm of crabs appears on the beach, these are events that demand to be seen. In each case, the event is newsworthy because it is visually and emotionally arresting. Reporters know this, and they so write accordingly. Scientists, whenever quoted, are thus speaking into a narrative that is already framed as an event that is worth staring at. Their words can therefore affect the shaping of interpretation, but they cannot undo the basic process of ecological disruption being experienced as a show. At this same time, the very word “*spectacle*” should not be conflated with meaning *triviality*. The public display of these animals, and the strong reactions that they evoke, are precisely what fix many of these events in local memory. People will remember the year a giant turtle came to the wharf, the day the beach turned red with crabs, or the time a “monster” fish was hauled into the harbor. What is much harder to remember, especially to those whose career does not revolve around it, are things such as the exact ocean temperature, or which current was running abnormally stronger than usual that week. What people remember, instinctively, is the animal, the crowd, and the collective feeling.

Scientific voices that are folded into the coverage have some of their greatest value in giving later readers a way to further recover environmental context, like hints about warm water currents, storms, or early climate reasoning that is somewhat buried within articles that, during their time, appeared mostly as human-interest stories. Ultimately, the newspaper clippings of this era all combine to suggest that the relationship between science and spectacle, especially along this particular stretch of the coast, has never been clean. Hopkins Marine Station, Fish and Game Department, and other institutions are not distant, abstract bodies of research or oversight. They

are physically present in the very same spaces where crowds gather to look at strange discoveries and different ecological phenomena. Scientists, game wardens, data analysts, etc., all possess incredibly unique minds with years of experience that provide us with innovative ways of observing and processing the world, but they are still human, still emotional, and still part of the audience, as well as being its interpreters. While their authority is real, it is exercised within a pre-existing shared cultural script, where the ocean is something that is wild and surprising and worth pausing our own daily activities to watch. This newspaper then becomes the place where all of these roles, whether expert or storyteller, come together to shape how marine change is understood by a community, long before phrases like “climate change” or “species range shifts” really took hold in public vocabulary.

IV. CONCLUSION

Taken altogether, these clippings from the *Monterey Peninsula Herald* show that rare visitors and anomalous events in Monterey Bay have always been understood through an interweaving of science and emotional memory. Events and appearances such as warm-water crabs, out-of-place turtles, and monstrous fishes act as signals of shifting currents or early climate reasoning, but much further than that, they get turned into anchors for local stories that organize time and emotion and turn marine change within their surroundings into one collective, shared experience. They are remembered through phrases like “not since 1859” or “first time in thirty years” as much as through formal measurements. The same stories that carried early discussions of changing currents and warming seas also carried emotional framings that turned certain animals into tragic victims, or malicious villains, and positioned some species as far easier to care about than others. Scientific voices from the Hopkins Marine Station, state

agencies, and local aquaria also do not stand apart from this process but work to interpret it, participate in it, and even sometimes complicate it, offering cautious explanations inside of scenes that have already been decided as worth gathering to watch. Reading these articles now suggests that before phrases such as “climate change” became popularly understood in public vocabulary, communities by the coast were already noticing and narrating their way through marine change for decades. The collection of newspaper articles that were analyzed for this paper preserve what was seen in Monterey Bay and also how it was specifically understood by different sorts of people, and it is that entanglement of observation and emotion that continues to shape which ocean stories ultimately persist.

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VI. SOURCES

Monterey Peninsula Herald (Monterey, California), 1932-1986. Historical newspaper clippings taken from the Monterey Public Library newspaper collection, compiled with the assistance of reference librarians and archivists. Individual articles cited in footnotes.